

Syntheses of some Pyrimido-2-carboxamidopyrazoline Derivatives

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Manuscript received 17 June 1991, revised 10 March 1992, accepted 10 April 1992

2-Acetoacetamidopyrimidine (2), prepared by heating 2-aminopyrimidine and ethyl acetoacetate at 160° was converted to pyrimido-2-carboxamide- α β -unsaturated-ketones (4) by the condensation with different aromatic aldehydes. The ketones on refluxing with hydrazine hydrate/phenyl hydrazine produced the title compounds 5 and 6

Pyrimidine derivatives are known to possess various physiological activities¹⁻⁵. On the other hand, amides containing heterocyclic moiety have been found to possess local anesthetic property². Again pyrazoline derivatives are claimed to have potential biological activity³. Considering all the above facts, it was thought that if pyrimidocarboxamido group was introduced to pyrazoline moiety, the resulting compounds may have some significant biological property.

For this purpose, 2-aminopyrimidine (1) was reacted with ethylacetoacetate to yield 2-acetoacetamidopyrimidine (2). Compound 2 was then converted into (4a-f) by fusing with different aromatic aldehydes (3a-f). The unsaturated ketones, 3-(pyrimido-2-carboxamido)-4-aryl-but-3-en-2-one (4a-f) was then separately condensed with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol and acetic acid to get 5a-f, and phenyl hydrazine in ethanol using piperidine as condensing agent to form (6a-f) (Scheme 1).

Compounds 5 and 6 responded the Knorr's colour test⁴, a characteristic test for arylpyrazoline. The structures were further confirmed by spectral data⁵.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tube and are uncorrected. The infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and the pmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer.

2-Acetoacetamidopyrimidine (2): A mixture of 2-aminopyrimidine (0.01 mol) and ethyl acetoacetate (0.02 mol) was heated at 160° for 3 h. After cooling, it was poured into water to remove unreacted 2-aminopyrimidine. The resulting solid was dried and crystallised from aqueous ethanol as colourless crystals (85%), m.p. 80°.

3-(Pyrimido-2-carboxamido-4-arylbut-2-one (4a-f): A mixture of 2 (0.01 mol) and the aromatic aldehyde (3a-f; 0.01 mol) was fused on an oil-bath at 100-140° for 1-2 h. The mass was then cooled, petroleum ether added and the resulting solid was

- a : R = *p*-nitrophenyl
 b : R = *m*-nitrophenyl
 c : R = 4-methoxy-3-hydroxyphenyl
 d : R = *o*-methoxyphenyl
 e : R = 2-pyridyl
 f : R = 2-furyl

Scheme 1

crystallised from suitable solvent; 4a (65%), m.p. 142° (EtOAc); δ (CDCl₃; 90 MHz) 2.43 (3H, s, COCH₃), 7.6 (s, *J*_B 18 Hz, C=CH) and 7.5-8.8 (7H, m, ArH); b (67%), 165° (EtOAc); c (62%), 72° (EtOAc/pet. ether); d (75%), 75° (MeOH); δ (CDCl₃; 90 MHz) 2.5 (3H, s, COCH₃), 4.42 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.56 (s, *J*_B 18 Hz, C=CH) and 7.2-8.6 (7H, m, ArH); e (63%), 74-75° (EtOH); f (50%), 70° (EtOH).

N-Acetyl-3-methyl-4-(pyrimidocarboxamido)-5-arylpyrazoline (5a-f): A mixture of 4a-f (0.005 mol), hydrazine hydrate (0.005 mol), ethanol (40 ml) and glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was refluxed for 10 h.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (5a-f, 6a-f)*

Compd. no.	M.p.** °C	Yield %	Colour	$\nu_{\max}$ (cm ⁻¹)	
5a	305 ^a	65	Golden yellow	1 635 (C=O), 1 600 (C=N), 835 (1,4-disubstituted-benzene)	—
b	192 ^b	70	Pale yellow	1 635 (C=O), 1 585 (C=N), 820 (1,4-disubstituted-benzene)	2.3 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.42 (3H, s, COCH ₃), 3.72 (2H, dd), 7.5-8.8 (7H, m, ArH)
c	175-77 ^b	70	Redish brown	—	—
d	>350 ^c	60	Yellow	—	—
e	63-65 ^d		Yellow	1 625 (C=O), 1 595 (C=N), 820 (1,4-disubstituted-benzene)	2.32 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.45 (3H, s, COCH ₃), 3.23 (2H, dd), 7.5-8.9 (12H, m, ArH)
f	180-81 ^e		Light yellow	—	—
6a	140-41 ^b	70	Light yellow	1 635 (C=O), 1 590 (C=N), 830 (1,4-disubstituted-benzene)	—
b	138-38 ^e	65	Yellow	—	2.42 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.10 (1H, dd, HA/JB 4.80 Hz), 3.72 (1H, dd, HB/KX 11.81 Hz), 7.2-8.6 (12H, m, ArH)
c	153 ^e	65	Brown	1 635 (C=O), 1 580 (C=N), 820 (1,3-disubstituted-benzene)	2.3 (3H, s, CH ₃), 4.42 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 3.23 (1H, dd, HA/JB 5.80 Hz), 3.96 (1H, dd, HB/KX 12.04 Hz), 7.5-8.9 (9H, m, ArH)
d	97 ^e	70	Brown	—	—
e	158-59 ^e	65	Redish brown	—	—
f	94-95 ^e	60	Redish brown	1 630 (C=O), 1 580 (C=N), 825 (1,3-disubstituted-benzene)	—

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

**Solvent for crystallisation : ^apyridine, ^bEtOAc+EtOH, ^cEtOH, ^dEtOAc, ^eMeOH.

The solution was then concentrated on a water-bath and then poured in ice-cold water. The resulting yellow solid was crystallised from suitable solvent (Table 1). The formation of pyrazolines were confirmed by Knorr's test.

N-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-(pyrimido-2-carboxamido)-5-arylpyrazoline (6a-f): A mixture of 4a-f (0.05 mol), phenyl hydrazine (0.005 mol), ethanol (40 ml) and piperidine (1 ml) was refluxed for 10-12 h. It was then concentrated, cooled and poured into acidified ice-cold water (5% HCl). The resulting solid was crystallised from proper solvents (Table 1). The formation of pyrazolines were confirmed by Knorr's test.

Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully acknowledge the facilities provided by the University Department of Chemistry, Bhagalpur University. Thanks are also extended to C.D.R.I., Lucknow for spectral recording.

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